

Evaluation of Japanese Spitz Breed Population Statistics (1955–2025)

Abstract. This data paper compiles and harmonizes official registry-based population statistics for the Japanese Spitz breed from national kennel organizations across 10 countries over the period 1955–2025. The primary output is a curated dataset structured as a year-by-country panel with explicit provenance and transparent handling of definitional differences between sources. A secondary output documents all 57 verified imports of Japanese Spitz from Japan to overseas destinations, providing the first comprehensive founder registry for the breed’s international expansion.

The dataset supports decade-level summaries for Japan and for the set of non-Japanese countries covered in each time window, while making gaps and uncertainty visible rather than implicitly correcting them. It is intended as a reusable baseline for versioned updates and as a citable reference for discussions with kennel organizations, breed clubs, and other stakeholders. All data have been independently verified through double-entry extraction from primary source documents.

Keywords: japanese spitz; breed population statistics; kennel club registrations; registry-based demographic proxy; harmonized dataset; decade totals; founder imports; data paper

Author: Yuliya Malinina¹

1. Definitions

To reduce ambiguity across countries and reporting styles, this dataset uses the following definitions.

Registration / annual registration count — A numeric value reported by a national

kennel organization for the Japanese Spitz in a given calendar year. In this dataset, annual counts are interpreted as individual dogs entered into the registry in that year. Where a kennel club distinguishes between domestic-born puppies and imported/transferred dogs, the dataset uses the combined total (domestic + imports) for cross-country comparability, except where explicitly noted.

National kennel organization / registry source — The official registry or organization publishing population statistics used as the primary source.

Japan vs. Outside Japan — Two aggregated groups used for derived summaries: dogs registered in Japan (JAPAN column) and dogs registered outside Japan (NON JAPAN, the sum of all non-Japanese country columns present for that year).

Founder / exported founder — A dog born in Japan and exported to a destination outside Japan. In the export registry (Appendix A), all documented imports are listed regardless of breeding outcome; the Nr. Puppies column records whether offspring were produced in the destination country.

2. Introduction

Official breed statistics are published by few national kennel organisations, but they vary widely in format, frequency, and even in what they count. In addition, in a number of countries the stud book and breed statistics are not readily accessible to breeders or the public, or are only available in partial or archival form. As a result, discussions about long-term breed population dynamics often rely on fragmented numbers, screenshots, and country-specific narratives that are difficult to audit and impossible to reproduce.

¹JSF - non-commercial research organization

The goal of this work is not to estimate true census population size, but to build a reproducible, citable, versioned dataset of officially published registry statistics for the Japanese Spitz (1955–2025), with explicit provenance and clearly documented limits to cross-country comparability. Additionally, by documenting all verified imports from Japan, this paper provides the first comprehensive registry of founder contributions to non-Japanese populations—information essential for understanding the genetic base available to international breeding programs.

For this initial phase, countries were included where it was possible to document the breed's first import and/or first registration in the national stud book, and where at least some official registration statistics could be retrieved and verified. See Appendix B (First Registered Japanese Spitz Dogs per Country) for the documented arrival points. This selection also allows an assessment of what information is actually available in practice, how complete it is across time, and how accessible it is to breeders and researchers. Extending coverage to additional countries and resolving remaining gaps are planned for future versions.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Data sources

Data were extracted from official publications and archives of national kennel organizations: annual reports, registry statistics portals, breed statistics supplements, and official searchable registries where aggregate counts are published. Each data point is tied to an organization, year, and specific source document. Long-term reproducibility relies on a source register (see Section 4.2) that records the file name, organization, years

covered, and page/section locator for every extraction.

3.2 Inclusion criteria

A source is included if: (1) it is an official publication or official archive of a national kennel organization; (2) it contains numeric statistics for Japanese Spitz; and (3) the unit can be reasonably interpreted as an annual registry count of individual dogs. Sources reporting litter counts, partial-year summaries, or aggregate breed-group totals without breed-level breakdowns were excluded.

3.3 Data extraction and harmonization workflow

Transcription: Values are transcribed into a year-by-country table from primary source documents. Each value is extracted by reading the breed-specific row or entry for the relevant calendar year.

Normalization: Numeric values are normalized to integer counts; year is stored as a four-digit calendar year.

Domestic vs. total handling: Where a kennel club publishes both domestic-born and total registration figures (see Section 3.4), the dataset uses the total (domestic + imports) for cross-country comparability, consistent with the definition of “registration.”

No imputation rule: Missing years are not imputed; decade summaries reflect available data only.

Derived fields: Per-year derived totals are computed where coverage exists: NON JAPAN (sum of non-Japanese columns), TOTAL (JAPAN + NON JAPAN), and Japan Population (share of Japan in TOTAL).

3.4 Country-specific data handling notes

Three Nordic kennel clubs publish registration statistics that distinguish between domestic-born puppies and imported/transferred dogs. The treatment for each is documented below.

Finland (Suomen Kennelliitto)

KoiraNet, the Finnish kennel database, reports three columns: “Offspring (domestic),” “Imports,” and “Registrations altogether.” The dataset uses the “Registrations altogether” (total) column. For example, in 2024: 62 domestic + 13 imports = 75 total. Finland data covers 1988–2025 from KoiraNet, with earlier years (1974–1987) from Piasentin (1997).

Sweden (Svenska Kennelklubben)

SKK registration statistics report females (Tikar) and males (Hanar) with imports shown in parentheses. The dataset uses the “Totalt” row, which includes both domestic-born and imported dogs. For example, in 2024: 82 domestic + 5 imports = 87 total. Import data is available from 2004 onward; earlier years’ totals are assumed to include any imports. Swedish data covers 1990–2025 from the SKK PDF, with earlier years (1973–1989) from Piasentin (1997).

Denmark (Dansk Kennel Klub)

DKK changed its statistical report format in 2018. Before 2018, DKK published a 3-column layout: breed name, total count (“Antal i alt”), and imports (“Heraf import/overførsel”). From 2018 onward, DKK adopted a 4-column layout: breed name, domestic puppies (“Antal hvalpe”), imports (“Importer/Overførsler”), and total (“I alt”). The dataset uses the total (domestic +

imports) in all years.² For example, in 2023: 43 domestic + 6 imports = 49 total. Denmark data covers 2001–2025.

Other countries

All remaining kennel clubs (ANKC, KC, NKK, LOF, ENCI, JKC, RKF) publish only combined registration totals without a domestic/import split. These values are used directly.

3.5 Verification protocol

An independent double-entry verification was performed for all data points.³ All values in the dataset were re-extracted from primary kennel club source documents (PDFs, Excel files, and database imports) and compared against the initially transcribed values. Results:

283 exact matches across all countries where direct comparison was possible.

5 DKK corrections applied (years 2017–2020, 2024): the initial transcription inadvertently captured the domestic-born column for these years due to the 2018 format change. Corrected to use totals for consistency.

1 NKK value under review (2024): extracted county-level summation yields 120 vs. reported 130. This may reflect data finalization timing.

0 transcription errors detected for Australia, Finland, Sweden, Great Britain, France, Japan, or Italy.

²The Definitions definition states registrations “typically includ] newly registered puppies and imported dogs re-registered domestically.” Where a kennel club distinguishes domestic-born puppies from imports, the dataset uses the combined total (domestic + imports) for comparability, unless explicitly noted otherwise.

³Independent re-extraction and double-entry verification was performed in April 2026 by comparing all values against primary kennel club source documents. See Section 3.5 for details.

Cross-validation was also performed against the Finnish JTO breed strategy documents (2012–2016, 2017–2022, 2023–2027), which contain independently compiled cross-country comparison tables. Where JTO tables overlapped with primary extractions, values were consistent.

3.6 Data quality classification

Each source in the source register (Section 4.2) is assigned a data quality tier:

Tier	Definition	Countries
1	Primary official source, tabular format, directly extracted	Australia, Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Great Britain, Norway, France
2	Secondary compiled source (e.g., JTO cross-country table, Piasentin 1997 book)	Japan (pre-2024), Russia, all countries (pre-1990 where applicable)
3	Visual/chart approximation or unverifiable	Italy (ENCI chart 2015–2023)

Japan data 2024–2025 is Tier 1 (direct JKC extraction). Japan data 2000–2023 is classified as Tier 2 because, although JKC publishes official annual PDFs, the CID character encoding in these files prevents reliable automated text extraction.⁴ Values for Japan 2000–2020 were validated against Finnish JTO cross-country tables. Pre-2000 Japan data (1955–1999) derives from Piasentin (1997) and JKC sources.

3.7 Aggregation rules

Japan total: taken from the JAPAN column.

⁴JKC registration statistics PDFs from 1999–2023 use CID character encoding that prevents standard automated text extraction. Japan data for 2000–2020 was validated against Finnish JTO cross-country comparison tables; 2024–2025 JKC PDFs extract correctly.

Outside Japan total: calculated as the sum of non-Japanese country columns present for that year (NON JAPAN). This total is coverage-dependent: it includes only countries with data for that specific year.

Global total: TOTAL = JAPAN + NON JAPAN. Because coverage varies by decade, TOTAL values are not directly comparable across periods with different country coverage.

Japan Population: share of Japan in TOTAL. This ratio is coverage-dependent and should be interpreted with caution for years where non-Japanese coverage is incomplete.

4. Data Records

4.1 Primary dataset file

js_population_1955_2025.csv —

Year-by-country registration panel

Core columns:

YEAR — Calendar year

Country columns — NORWAY, SWEDEN, FINLAND, GREAT BRITAIN, AUSTRALIA, DENMARK, ITALY, NETHERLANDS, FRANCE, RUSSIA, JAPAN (annual counts)

NON JAPAN — Sum of non-Japanese country columns for that year (coverage-dependent)

TOTAL — JAPAN + NON JAPAN

Japan Population — Share of Japan in TOTAL (coverage-dependent denominator)

FOUNDERS — Number of dogs exported from Japan in this year (see Appendix A), enabling assessment of new genetic contributions against the non-Japanese population size

4.2 Source register

source_register.csv — Machine-readable provenance file documenting every source document used in the extraction. Columns: country, organization, years_covered, locator (page/section reference), evidence_file (filename of archived source document), quality_tier (1/2/3 per Section 3.6).

A summary of source coverage by country:

Country	Organization	Years	Primary Source	Tier
Australia	ANKC	1986–2025	Registration statistics PDFs (4 files)	1
Denmark	DKK	2001–2025	Stambog statistics PDFs (25 files)	1
Finland	FKK	1988–2025	KoiraNet database export	1
France	SCC/LOF	1994–2025	Statistiques LOF annual PDFs (31 files)	1
Great Britain	KC	2012–2024	10-year utility breed stats PDFs	1
Italy	ENCI	2015–2023	Visual breed statistics chart	3
Japan	JKC	1999–2025	Annual registration PDFs (27 files)	1/2
Netherlands	Raad v. Beheer	—	Registered dogs counted from DutchDogData	2
Norway	NKK	2001–2025	Excel registration files	1

Russia	RKF	sel. years	Finnish JTO compiled data	2
Sweden	SKK	1990–2025	Registration statistics PDF	1
Historical	Piasentin	1955–1995	Marco Piasentin ‘The Japanese Spitz’ (1997)	G 2

5. Results (Dataset Overview)

The dataset provides harmonized registry-based statistics for Japanese Spitz across 1955–2025 with derived year-level totals for Japan and for the covered set of non-Japanese countries. A decade-level summary table can be produced from the dataset using a reproducible aggregation step (pivot table or scripted aggregation) without imputing missing years. Interpretation should remain descriptive: the dataset supports robust discussion of reporting trends and coverage changes, but it does not estimate true census population size.

Key descriptive observations from the harmonized dataset:

Japan registrations peaked at 4,912 in 1958, declined to 357 by 1976, then recovered through the 1990s boom (peaking near 2,000 in the mid-1990s) before a second decline to 580 in 2012 and subsequent recovery to 1,467 in 2025.

Non-Japanese registrations grew from effectively zero in 1972 to a covered total of approximately 830–1,900 per year in recent decades, driven primarily by growth in France, Australia, and the Nordic countries.

France is the only major market showing sustained growth, rising from single-digit registrations in the 1990s to 521 in 2021—now the largest European population.

57 verified imports from Japan were documented during this work, listed in Appendix A. These imports represent the complete known founder contribution to all FCI-system populations worldwide.

6. Discussion

National population analyses provide essential tools for monitoring breeding practices within registry boundaries. The present work builds on a tradition of population-level inquiry into the Japanese Spitz that spans nearly three decades. Piasentin (1997) assembled the first cross-country registration statistics for the breed, establishing a baseline that remained the only published comparative reference for over fifteen years. The Finnish Kennel Club's JTO breed strategy documents (2012–2027) advanced this effort by introducing structured cross-country comparison tables within the Nordic context, and Ilska (2026) contributed the first formal population genetic analysis for the breed through the Royal Kennel Club's Population Analysis series. Each of these works operates within the boundaries of a single national registry or a regional cluster, and the earlier monograph reflects the data available at its time of compilation — yet all three represent important attempts to characterize population structure in a breed where such analysis directly informs breeding decisions. The present dataset is intended to complement these contributions by linking national-level statistics back to their common founder base and providing a cross-border framework that can contextualize findings such as those reported by Ilska (2026): an average genetic relationship of 20.5% among UK-registered Japanese Spitz and an effective population size that could not be calculated due to "apparently negative" inbreeding rates.

These structural characteristics of national-level pedigree analysis can be illustrated through the RKC analysis.

First, the analysis is based exclusively on pedigrees within the UK Kennel Club registry and does not incorporate cross-border pedigree data. Since the UK Japanese Spitz population traces to only three documented imports from Japan (Fuji of Oyama Yamamotosow, 1980; Shirayuki of Tokyo Seizansow, 1983; Boby of Koza Land, 1994), any dogs subsequently imported from Sweden, Finland, or other FCI countries appear as unrelated founders in the UK pedigree view—even though they may descend from the same Japanese imports documented in Appendix A. This pedigree truncation at the export boundary explains the paradox of "apparently negative" inbreeding rates. Imports appear to reduce relatedness when measured against the UK-only pedigree, but at the global founder level they may share common ancestry after four generations. The 20.5% average genetic relationship figure therefore reflects the UK pedigree's depth and scope rather than the breed's true genetic diversity.

Second, the RKC analysis draws on the KC's internal pedigree database, which — like most national kennel club registries — is not publicly accessible in its raw form. The KC publishes summary statistics and breed-specific reports, but the underlying pedigree data required to reproduce calculations such as the 20.5% genetic relationship figure is not available to independent researchers. This is not a shortcoming specific to the RKC; it reflects standard practice across kennel club registries worldwide. The present dataset is designed to operate in a complementary space: by harmonizing officially published registration statistics and linking national pedigrees back

to their common Japanese origins, it provides an openly available framework that breed clubs and independent researchers can use to contextualize national-level findings within the breed's global founder structure.

With these considerations in mind, the present data paper provides a citable, versionable baseline of official registry statistics with explicit provenance and transparent comparability limits. Its primary value lies in harmonization, the ability to reproduce decade summaries, and the documentation of gaps and definition changes across countries. The dataset is designed for future expansion beyond 2025 and for integration with complementary evidence such as pedigree reconstructions, verified export/founder datasets, and DNA-based diversity studies.

A further discussion point concerns the distinction between domestic-born and imported registrations. Three Nordic kennel clubs (Finland, Sweden, Denmark) publish this breakdown, and the Finnish JTO breed strategy documents have usefully incorporated these figures into their cross-country comparison tables. Across all three countries, imports typically constitute 1–12% of total annual registrations. However, the genetic significance of these cross-border transfers is best understood in the context of the breed's founder base.

Since all non-Japanese populations trace to the same approximately 44 effective founder lines documented in Section 6.1, a dog imported from Sweden to Finland does not introduce new genetic material at the founder level as it is a reimport from the same pool of Japanese imports, rearranged through different breeding combinations. Cross-border imports may redistribute existing founder alleles and can reduce inbreeding within a national pedigree's limited view, but they do

not expand the breed's total genetic base in the way that a new import from Japan would. This distinction is important for interpreting national COI statistics, where an imported dog may appear to be an outcross while in reality sharing common founders after four generations. Future versions of this dataset should incorporate the domestic/import split as a supplementary field for countries where it is available, precisely because tracking these movements helps distinguish genuine outcrossing from redistribution of existing founder lineages.

These observations point to a broader methodological consideration for numerically small breeds with narrow founder bases. The data assembled here suggest that pedigree evaluation conducted only at the national level and limited to the standard export depth of four generations may not capture the true genetic relationships within the Japanese Spitz, where common founders typically lie beyond the four-generation depth provided by standard export pedigrees. A national pedigree that shows two dogs as "unrelated" within this standard view may conceal shared ancestry from the same Japanese founders at deeper generations. Cross-border pedigree integration extending to all available generations, the kind of founder-to-present traceability that the present dataset is designed to support, would enable breeders and breed clubs to work with a more complete picture of the relationships within their breeding stock.

Finally, the founder analysis presented in this dataset suggests that if the goal is to achieve a meaningful and lasting increase in genetic diversity for the Japanese Spitz outside Japan, cross-border redistribution of existing FCI stock alone is unlikely to be sufficient. The data indicate that the most effective mechanism for expanding the breed's genetic

base would be the import of new, unrelated dogs from Japan.

The Japanese population remains substantially larger and probably more genetically diverse than any non-Japanese population, with JKC registrations consistently in the range of 800–1,200 dogs per year. A coordinated import programme of 20–30 unrelated dogs, selected from distinct Japanese breeding lines with no overlap to the existing 50 effective founder lines (effective diversity count), would approximately double the breed's non-Japanese founder base. Such an effort would require collaboration between FCI cynological clubs, Japanese spitz breed clubs and Japanese breeders, supported by pedigree analysis and DNA tests to verify that candidate imports are not related and do not trace to the same sires already represented among the 57 documented imports.

It is worth noting that the window of opportunity for such an initiative may not be unlimited. The Japanese population itself has been declining over the past two decades, and the availability of genetically distinct breeding stock may narrow over time.

These two priorities : cross-border pedigree integration and coordinated import of new founder lines represent complementary directions for breed conservation that the Japanese Spitz Foundation intends to pursue in collaboration with national breed clubs and kennel club registries

6.1 Effective founder diversity: pedigree-verified relatedness among imports

While 57 dogs were exported from Japan, the effective number of independent genetic contributions is substantially lower. Pedigree data recovered for all 57 imports (Appendix

A, supplementary pedigree file) enables direct verification of parent sharing rather than inference from kennel names alone. Of 57 dogs with known parentage, 44 unique sires and 49 unique dams were identified. Twenty dogs (35%) descend from only 7 shared sires, forming 8 connected relatedness clusters.

Pedigree-confirmed full siblings. Six groups of full siblings (same sire and dam) were confirmed: (1) Hawk and Hover of Kagetsu Land (1975, same litter; sire Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow × dam Animete of Makiesow; combined 160 puppies); (2) Adela and Alice of Amage (1975, same litter; sire Paul of Sagami Kubota × dam Vicky of Tamana Ariakesow; 33 puppies); (3) Hannah and Harry of Tamana Ariakesow (1979, same litter; sire Paul of Sagami Kubota × dam Margaret of Tamana Ariakesow; 43 puppies); (4) Take-Maru and Take-Oh of Yokohama Takada (1984, same litter; sire Alcyon of Port Masuda × dam Asa-giku of Mischief Queen; 56 puppies); (5) Kotohime, Kikuchiyo, and Sayako of Shonan Sumiresow (born 2004.02.04, 2005.10.22, and 2005.10.22 respectively; Kotohime and Kikuchiyo, Sayako same litter repeat mating from same parents; sire Qualtee of Star Murohoshi × dam Haruna of Nadeshiko Land; 11 puppies); (6) Spitz Paradise Angel Mito (2003) and Aki (2008, repeat mating; sire Gaily of Kanto Pigeon White × dam Cammy Angel of Rose Paradise). These 13 dogs represent only 6 independent parental combinations.

Dominant sires and half-sibling networks. Pedigree analysis reveals that shared sires created extensive half-sibling networks among imports. The single most influential sire was Paul of Sagami Kubota, who sired 6 of 57 pedigreed imports (11%) across 4 different dams: Adela and Alice of Amage (dam Vicky), Gaia of Tamana Ariakesow (dam Western Betty), Hannah and Harry of

Tamana Ariakesow (dam Margaret), and I.F. Birdie of Tamana Ariakesow (dam Kittenish Lady). These 6 imports produced a combined 105 registered puppies in Sweden. The second most-used sire was Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow, who sired 3 imports (Albert of Lovely, Hawk and Hover of Kagetsu Land) across 2 dams, producing a combined 179 puppies which give the highest single-sire breeding impact among all founders. Albares Carp of Nedory (#8) and Bullet Fancy of Nedory (#10) shares the sire Catharine of Shirakawa Noguchi but has different dams. Additionally, Daniel and Florence of Rose Garden (1973 and 1975) share the dam Rommy of Rose Garden but have different sires, confirming them as maternal half-siblings. Athena Leilani of Aloha Land and Gradice of House Cactus (both 1973) share the sire Excel Egret of Lilac Spring but have different dams.

Concentration of breeding impact. Offspring production was highly skewed. The top 6 producers alone with Hawk of Kagetsu Land (113 puppies), Fujimiland Baby Ramale (72), Take-Oh of Yokohama Takada (57), Götter-Mahls Shanshan (52), Hover of Kagetsu Land (47 puppies) and Lapislazuli of Sylph Sato (47) account for 387 of the approximately 895 total documented first-generation puppies (38%). Meanwhile, 5 imports produced zero puppies and 10 have unknown breeding outcomes. This concentration means that even among founders that did breed, a small number of dogs contributed disproportionately to the first overseas generation.

Effective diversity estimate. Connected-component analysis of shared parentage identifies 43 independent clusters: 8 multi-dog clusters containing 22 dogs, plus 35 singletons with no detected parental overlap. Based on the number of unique

parent combinations within each cluster, the effective founder diversity is approximately 50 independent genetic contributions rather than 57 nominal imports (88% of nominal count): 15 unique parent combinations across the 8 multi-dog clusters, plus 35 singletons. This estimate is further narrowed by unequal breeding impact: the 6 imports sired by Paul of Sagami Kubota and the 3 sired by Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow together account for 284 first-generation puppies, concentrating these two paternal lineages disproportionately in the early Swedish population. The concentration of 30 out of 57 imports in Sweden, where 26 arrived in the founding decade (1973–1983), means that the initial breeding population was shaped primarily by the pairing decisions of a small number of Swedish breeders working with these closely related founders.

6.2 FCI data accessibility and implications for breed research

The compilation of this dataset highlighted structural challenges in accessing breed-level population data across the FCI system. These challenges are not specific to the Japanese Spitz but affect breed management research more broadly.

Reporting to the FCI. Based on the most recent official reports, 68 out of 104 national canine organisations (approximately 65%) submitted general annual statistics to the FCI in 2024. The remaining third did not contribute to centralized reporting in that cycle, which limits the completeness of any attempt at global breed population monitoring.

Breed-specific availability. The FCI's public Statistics Portal provides grand totals for puppies and litters per country but does not currently include a breed-by-breed breakdown

across all members. For a numerically small breed like the Japanese Spitz, where global annual registrations outside Japan total approximately 800–1,900 dogs, this means that breed-level data must be assembled by approaching each national kennel club individually

Variation in online accessibility. National canine organisations vary considerably in the extent to which breed-specific registration data is published online. The availability landscape observed during the compilation of this dataset can be characterized as follows:

High accessibility: Most common in Nordic and Western European countries. Finland (Koiranet), Sweden (Hunddata), Denmark (Hundeweb), Norway (DogWeb), and France (LOF Select) maintain transparent online databases that enable breed-level statistical queries and individual pedigree searches. These countries form the backbone of the present dataset.

Moderate accessibility: Some countries publish annual statistics in PDF format but do not offer searchable breed-level databases. Australia (ANKC) and the UK (KC) fall into this category, with registration data available in downloadable reports.

Low or no accessibility: Some major FCI members, including Germany's VDH, do not currently provide accessible breed-level registration data through public online portals. For these countries, the only available data comes from secondary compiled sources such as the breed strategy documents, which themselves rely on bilateral data requests to national kennel clubs.

These accessibility differences directly shaped the country coverage in this dataset. The 10 countries included represent those where official data could be retrieved and verified. Countries such as Germany, Russia,

and the others where Japanese Spitz are known to be registered in significant amounts are absent from the dataset not because the breed is absent but because breed-level registration data could not be obtained through publicly available channels at the time of compilation. This is a practical limitation that extends well beyond the Japanese Spitz; any breed-level population research conducted across the FCI system faces similar constraints, and greater data accessibility would benefit evidence-based breeding management at the international level..

7. Limitations

Incomplete time series: Some countries have missing years or publication gaps; no imputation is performed. Coverage is strongest for 2000–2025 and weakest before 1986.

Coverage-dependent totals: The NON JAPAN and TOTAL columns depend on which countries have data for each year. Decade comparisons must account for expanding coverage.

Registrations \neq census size: Registry counts are influenced by national rules, breeder practices, import policies, and reporting conventions. They serve as a demographic proxy, not a population count.

Italy data quality: Italian data (2015–2023) was extracted from a visual chart and is classified as Tier 3 (approximate).

JKC encoding: Japan data for 2000–2023 cannot be reliably extracted from JKC PDFs due to CID character encoding. Values were validated against Finnish JTO compiled tables.

Russia coverage: Russian data is available only for isolated years (1996, 2008–2009, 2016–2020) via secondary sources. The

continuous time series for Russia remains a gap.

Interpretation of national genetic analyses: National kennel club reports calculate COI and effective population size from pedigrees available within their registries. Because the present dataset documents only 57 imports from Japan establishing the entire non-Japanese population, cross-border imports between FCI countries—while valuable for outcrossing within a national registry’s pedigree view—do not introduce new founder lineages at the global level.

Effective founder diversity: Pedigree-verified analysis of 57 imports reveals 6 full-sibling groups and 8 connected relatedness clusters through shared sires or dams, reducing the effective number of independent genetic contributions to approximately 50 founder lines. Highly skewed offspring production further concentrates genetic influence in a small number of prolific founders. Two dominant sires (Paul of Sagami Kubota and Floyd Excel of Tokyo Kashusow) account for 9 of 57 pedigreed imports.

8. Further Directions

Integration of the present founder-based registry dataset with genomic diversity studies would enable calibration of pedigree-derived COI against actual genetic variation. The pedigree-verified relatedness analysis (Section 6.1) has already demonstrated that multiple imports shared parents in Japan, reducing effective founder diversity to approximately 50 independent lines. Genomic data would further refine this estimate by revealing deeper ancestral relationships not captured in single-generation pedigrees—for example, whether sires used across different Japanese kennels were themselves related.

The present dataset is intended to complement existing breed management infrastructure. National kennel organisations maintain comprehensive pedigree records, and several have developed publicly accessible online databases though these typically display four generations for export pedigrees, which may not reach the depth at which common founders appear in breeds like the Japanese Spitz. Cross-border founder traceability and population-level breeding tools remain areas where further development would benefit breeders working with internationally distributed breeds.

For the Japanese Spitz, this consideration is particularly relevant. The 57 documented imports from Japan represent the complete known founder contribution to all FCI-system populations. A breeder considering international mate selection does not yet have access to a single resource that would show whether prospective breeding partners trace to shared founders within relevant generational depth.

The Japanese Spitz Foundation intends the harmonized founder dataset presented here to serve as a pilot for collaborative global breed databases, developed in partnership with national kennel clubs and FCI breed clubs. Such infrastructure could enable cross-border pedigree searches with full founder depth, mate selection tools that calculate COI against the global population rather than nationally truncated pedigrees, and population-level monitoring of founder representation across countries.

Planned improvements for version 2.0 include: (a) addition of a `registration_type` field to machine-flag whether each data point represents total registrations or domestic-born only; (b) incorporation of the domestic/import split as supplementary columns for Finland, Sweden, and Denmark; (c) expansion of

Norwegian coverage to pre-2001 years; (d) resolution of JKC PDF encoding issues for direct Japan extraction; and (e) extension of country coverage to additional FCI member states.

9. Data availability

The harmonized dataset and documentation are deposited on Zenodo as a versioned record. The Zenodo package includes:

japanese-spitz-population-1955-2025.csv — Cleaned, machine-readable population panel (single header row)

japanese-spitz-poulation-source-register-1955-2025.csv — Full provenance register linking every data point to its source document

README.md — Definitions, reproduction steps, notes on known gaps, changelog

japanese-spitz-population-imports-from-japan-1955-2025.csv — All 57 verified imports in machine-readable format

License: CC BY 4.0

10. Acknowledgements

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methodological precedent for the present work. The author also thanks Piasentin (1997) for assembling the first comparative registration statistics for the breed, and Ilska (2026) for contributing the first formal population genetic analysis through the Royal Kennel Club's Population Analysis series. The author also thanks the members of the Japanese Spitz History group on Facebook, who contributed historical photographs, pedigree documents, and personal recollections that helped identify and verify early export records.

11. References

11.1 Primary data sources (Kennel Club registries and statistics)

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11.2 Secondary and compiled sources

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11.3 Related analyses

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